

Fig. 2 Banat GIS map illustrating earthquakes and epicenters of earthquakes. The map support is Open Street Map

The main objective is focused on identifying natural laboratories for the study of monitoring methods in areas with natural emissions and making measurements of the CO₂ stream (surveys the soil-gas) in Harghita and Banat. The identification and documentation activities for laboratories with natural emissions of CO₂ from Banat and Harghita, has been to collect geological data, geophysical and geochemical on natural emissions of CO₂ in the both areas. From the collected data (specialized scientific papers, books, geological and geophysical maps, travel guides (including data on mofettes) and previous geochemical studies of natural CO₂ emissions), the sites of interest, the development of GIS maps for both areas were identified, as well as highlighting the mechanisms of CO₂ migration to the surface.

Several measurements of gas emissions in the wet and dry mofettes were made both on the surface of the investigation perimeters and in the area of mud volcanoes. Geophysical measurements of electrometric type and GPR (Ground Penetrating Radar) will be performed in the next period. The results of these measurements will be used to define the local geophysical model and improve the geological model, but also for a subsequent correlation with the measurements of CO₂ flux from the soil. We will be able to make recommendations regarding the possibility of using these methods in monitoring the geological storage sites of CO₂. The geological model will highlight fractures and faults of local character, these being the routes of CO₂ migration to the surface.

The two zones have different geological structures, and the origin of CO₂ emissions in the two areas is related to the magmatic activity, the magmatism of the Eastern Carpathians in Harghita and the neogene magmatism of the Apuseni Mountains in Banat.

The structural model of Banat is closely correlated with the strong tectonization of the sedimentary cover. The overall picture is that of horsts (lifting areas) and rattlesnakes (lowering areas).

Fig. 3 Neotectonic activity and eastern seismicity of Pannonian depression (Polonic 1985).

1. Pre-neogene formations, 2. Pliocene subsidence / Quaternary elevation, 3. Pannonian subsidence / Pliocene elevation, 4. Sarmatian rise / Quaternary subsidence, 5. Badenian subsidence /, 6. Pliocene subsidence, 7. quaternary subsidence, 8. faults, 9. epicenters (after Diconescu M., 1997)

The Banat area overlaps geologically with the southern section of the Pannonian Depression. A feature of this sector is that the crystalline foundation, penetrated by eruptive masses, is covered directly by Miocene and Pliocene deposits with thicknesses over 5000 m. Only isolated, below Miocene, there are Cretaceous-Upper and Eocene deposits (Paraschiu, 1975). One of the major morpho- structural elements is the major lifting area Seceani - Călăcea - Satchinez, which seems to represent a buried branch of the Poiana Ruscă mountains. From Seceani to Șandra, at a distance of about 25 km, the crystalline foundation sinks with 1150 m. Between the Arad-Turnu and Seceani-Șandra massifs, the graben Varș is formed with maximum depths of 3200 m. The last-mentioned mountain massif delimits towards north another area of lowering of the foundation, with depths of maximum 2800 m. The geographical centre of this depression, which does not correspond with the lowest area, is marked by the course of the Timiș river. To SV, the Timis depression is closed on the bend of the Banat Carpathians.

The tectonic blocks are separated by active, deep faults. This is also confirmed by the occurrence of thermal and mineral water springs (Biled, Călăcea, Timișoara, Buziaș, Pișchia, Lipova, Ivanda) and mofettes (Buziaș), with releases of CO₂, radon helium, argon and other gases of crustal origin (Uruioac et. al., 2011).

In the Buziaș they were made measurements on Companies SPA Treatment BUZIAȘ S.A. (S.C.T.B. BUZIAȘ S.A.), in the place arranged for a capture from the nearby drill, where the CO₂ concentration is almost 100%.

Another area where gas emissions were identified is located between Timisoara and Arad. It is a swampy area with very large area extension. From the collected data, it was found that the activity of gas emissions or mud volcanoes is seasonal and is evidenced by the hydrological regime of the respective season.

Fig. 4 Mud volcanoes with temporary activity in the Fibiș Valley

The deep geological structure of the *Harghita area* was highlighted after performed series of studies, gravimetric works (I. Gavăt et al., 1968) and electrometric measurements for determining the depth and foundation of the Gheorgheni basin (Cr. Mihail, 1970). The important structural element is given by the deep fault and the assembly of the fault lines in the deep area of Harghita county. These slices were divided into three categories: crustal faults (G4, G7, G8, G9 and G13); regional faults (g25, g26) and local faults (L1, L3, L4-8). These fault systems (Figure 1) represent the access and distribution routes in volume and surface of the post-volcanic emissions.

From the hydrogeological research made in the county of Harghita an extensive mophetic aureole have been delimited that affects all the major geological units in the region. Depending on the mofetic occurrences or the carbonated waters on its surface, the outline of the mophetic aureole may present changes.

Fig. 5 Geological map for Hargita area

The genesis of carbonated mineral waters is given by the interference of the mofetic carbon dioxide (CO₂) with the aquifer layers in the geological formations structured in the major units mentioned above.

The petrographic type of these formations conditions the specific hydrochemical nature of mineral waters. Depending on the geological formations crossed, the conditions of accumulation and the needles for the circulation of the water, different types of mineral waters have been identified (A. Pricăjan, 1969).

Dry gas emissions (mofettes) occur on the magmatic line - the major crustal fault. Such emanations were highlighted by measurements made in mofettes (Harghita Băi), in dry builded mofettes (Sântimbru Băi), in unbuilded mofettes (Vermed, Lăzărești), wet and dry mofettes and in the bath area (Balványos-Băile Apor), in dry mofettes with H₂S (Crater Cucu, Sântimbru Băi), in builded mofettes without H₂S (Băile Tușnad), in caves (Balványos, Băile Balványos, Sulfuroasa Caves).

References

- Airinei S., Pricăjan A. (1972). Corelații între structura geologică adâncă și aureola mofetică din județul Harghita, cu privire la zonele de apariție a apelor minerale carbogazoase. Stud. cerc. geol., geofiz., geogr., seria Geol., Acad. R. S. România, București, 17 / 2, p. 245 – 258
- Frunzeti N., Baciuc C. (2012). Diffuse CO₂ Emission at Sfânta Ana Lake-Filled Crater (Eastern Carpathians, Romania). Procedia Environmental Sciences, Volume 14, 2012, Pages 188-194
- Kis B.M., Ionescu A., Harangi S., Palcsu L., Etiope G., Calin B. (2016). Gas geochemical survey of long dormant Ciomadul volcano (South Harghita Mts., Romania): constraints on the flux and origin of fluids. Geophysical Research Abstracts Vol. 18, EGU2016-9576, 2016. EGU General Assembly 2016
- Paraschiv (1975). Geologia zăcămintelor de hidrocarburi din România. Institutul De Geologie Și Geofizică. Studii Tehnice și Economice. București
- Uruic S., Mășu A., Sinitean A., Albușescu M., Popovici H. (2011). Preliminary study of mud volcanoes in Banat (Southwest Romania). Geo-Eco-Marina, nr. 17, p. 245-249